

SYNTHESIS OF A TRIPHENYLSULPHANE SYSTEM

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Thionyl chloride reacts with dimethylaniline producing hexamethyl-triaminotriphenylsulphane. In the presence of an inert solvent tetramethyldiaminodiphenylsulphoxide is formed and the latter may be condensed with another molecule of dimethylaniline forming the dye, hexamethyl-triaminotriphenylsulphane.

Michaelis (*Annalen*, 1904, 274, 173, 180) has reported that both aliphatic and aromatic primary amines react with thionyl chloride to yield thionyl amines,

(where R=alkyl or aryl group). The primary aryl amines give blue coloured compounds sparingly soluble in water, when the reaction is carried out in the absence of a solvent. The secondary amines on the other hand are known to react with thionyl chloride only in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to give substituted diphenyl sulphoxides.

As there is no reference to the action of SOCl_2 on a tertiary amine, we took up the study of the reaction of thionyl chloride with dimethylaniline as a typical tertiary amine. The reaction has been carried out both in the presence of an inert solvent such as petroleum ether and in its absence. In the absence of the solvent thionyl chloride reacts with dimethylaniline at room temperature liberating dense greenish white fumes and producing a heavily coloured blue dye. The reaction has been next carried out at the temperature of ice, and the colour base of the dye is precipitated by ammonia, as faintly coloured and tarry in nature. It is dried in vacuum for over two weeks, then dissolved in chloroform and converted into the hydrochloride by passing hydrochloric acid gas into the chloroform solution. The hydrochloride, so obtained, is also tarry and may be dried in vacuum to a blue powder that cannot be crystallised, m.p. $108-12^\circ$. All attempts at crystallising the dye as a double oxalate also failed.

The formation of the dye may be formulated as follows:—

The conversion of (I) into (II) bears a close analogy to the conversion of Michler's ketone into malachite green.

The above proposed mechanism of the formation of the dye is based on the following evidence. Michaelis (*loc. cit.*) has reported the formation of sulphoxide derivatives by the interaction of thionyl chloride and monomethylaniline in the presence of aluminium chloride. As the *para* position of dimethylaniline is very active a similar condensation would take place in the case of this tertiary base giving the compound (I) even without the use of a condensing agent. Such a condensation product has actually been isolated by us by carrying out the reaction between thionyl chloride and dimethylaniline in the presence of an inert solvent like petroleum ether at the temperature of ice. The reddish yellow tarry product, first obtained after crystallisation from methyl alcohol, gives colourless cubes, m.p. 243-44°. The molecular weight as determined by the Rast's method is in agreement with the formula (I),

The sulphoxide (I), thus obtained, has been condensed further with one molecule of dimethylaniline in the presence of phosphorous oxychloride to give the dye (II).

The blue dye, thus obtained, is structurally similar to a triphenylmethane dye; in its observed properties it shows similarity to such dyestuffs. It is found to be a basic dye which dyes cotton, silk and artificial silk from a tannin-mordanted bath. Like basic dyes, it is not fast to sunlight when dyed on cotton. However, it is found to be much faster on artificial silk.

The dye forms lakes with aluminium and zinc salts; with the addition of zinc chloride and alkali the lake is obtained in the form of a blue powder. The aluminium lake, when freshly prepared, is soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid but after standing for some days it is rendered insoluble. The zinc lake is soluble in dilute acids.

The chloride of the dye gives a pure shade of blue on cotton, and the acetate a violet-blue; with alkali an almost colourless dye base is precipitated which can be re-converted into the dye by the addition of acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hexamethyltriaminotriphenylsulphane.—To dimethylaniline (24.3 c.c.), placed in a round-bottomed flask and cooled to -10° , was added thionyl chloride (10 c.c.) dropwise, with constant stirring, during a period of 1 hour. The reaction proceeded violently in the beginning but gradually subsided; after standing for 2 hours, a further quantity of dimethylaniline (20 c.c.) was added to the reaction mixture and the whole heated on a water-bath for 6 hours in a current of dry hydrochloric acid gas.

The reaction mixture was then thrown into cold water (500 c.c.) when the impure dye was precipitated; it was dissolved in hot water and the dye base precipitated by the addition of sodium carbonate solution; the excess of the dimethylaniline was removed by steam-distillation. The dye base was then dissolved in hydrochloric acid, cooled by addition of ice and the dye precipitated by the addition of iced ammoniacal brine. The dye was then filtered off at the pump. It is a viscous tarry product which does not crystallise from any one of the common solvents. A solution in dry pyridine was allowed to evaporate slowly in a vacuum desiccator when at the end of two weeks, a dark blue powder was obtained, m.p. 108-12°. (Found: C, 56.1; H, 5.9; N, 7.62;

S, 5'60; M.W., 458. $C_{24}H_{22}N_2Cl_2S$ requires C, 57'6; H, 6'4; N, 8'4; S, 6'4 per cent. M.W., 500'5).

Tetramethyldiaminodiphenylsulphoxide.—An excess of thionyl chloride (6 c.c.), dissolved in petroleum ether (50 c.c.), was added in small portions at a time, during a period of half an hour to a solution of dimethylaniline (10 c.c.) in petroleum ether (100 c.c.), cooled to 0°. The hydrochloride of the sulphoxide was precipitated out as a tarry product. The petroleum was removed by distillation under reduced pressure; the product, still a tarry one, was then freed from excess of thionyl chloride by shaking with petroleum ether. It was then dried in a vacuum desiccator for several days and finally crystallised from methyl alcohol with great difficulty in fine cubes, m.p. 243-44°; yield 78%. (Found: N, 7'59; Cl, 19'2; S, 8'71; M. W. 353. $C_{18}H_{22}ON_2Cl_2S$ requires N, 7'76; Cl, 19'4; S, 8'86 per cent. M.W., 361.)

Condensation of the Sulphoxide with Dimethylaniline.—A solution of the sulphoxide (10 g.) in dimethylaniline (20 c.c.) was heated with phosphorus oxychloride (10 c.c.) on the water-bath for 2 hours.

The contents of the flask were poured into water (500 c.c.), rendered just alkaline with sodium carbonate and distilled in steam. The product, when free from dimethylaniline, was dissolved in hydrochloric acid cooled to 10° and the dye precipitated by the addition of ammoniacal brine. It was dissolved in dry pyridine and was allowed to crystallise and the tarry product dried in vacuum for several days, m.p. 110-14°, the m.p. with the dye originally obtained being depressed by 3-4°. (Found: C, 55'9; H, 6'0; N, 7'48; Cl, 20'5; S, 5'3. $C_{24}H_{22}N_2Cl_2S$ requires C, 57'60; H, 6'4; N, 8'4; Cl, 21'2; S, 6'4 per cent).

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